

Supplementary Figure 3: Time-dependent uptake of fluorescent glycan conjugates by *B. theta*. **A**) Change in mean fluorescence intensity of *B. theta* (white) and Bt Δ MAN1/2/3 (dashed) incubated with FLA-YM and a control (*B. theta* incubated with unlabeled YM, black) over time (0* (true zero), 0 (directly after glycan addition), 24 and 72 hours). **B**) Change in mean fluorescence intensity of *B. theta* (white) and Bt Δ RGII (dashed) incubated with FLA-RGII and a control (*B. theta* incubated with unlabeled RGII, black) over time (0* (true zero), 0 (directly after glycan addition), 24 and 72 hours). N=8,500 and error bars = standard deviation.